

1 *This is an Accepted Manuscript of an article published by Taylor &*
2 *Francis in Immunotherapy on 17 May 2023, available at:*
3 <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.2217/imt-2023-0037>
4

1 **Upadacitinib for moderate to severe atopic dermatitis.**

2 Navarro-Triviño, Francisco; Alcántara-Luna, Sara; Domínguez-Cruz,
3 Javier; Galán-Gutiérrez, Manuel; Ruiz-Villaverde, Ricardo; Pereyra-
4 Rodríguez, José-Juan; Armario-Hita, José-Carlos

5

6 Corresponding autor:

7 José Juan Pereyra-Rodríguez

8 Hospital Universitario Virgen del Rocio

9 email: jpereyra@us.es

10

1 Type: drug evaluation

2
3 ABSTRACT

4 Atopic dermatitis is an inflammatory skin disease whose prevalence has increased in the
5 last decade. It affects all age groups, with adult involvement being a major focus of
6 interest in recent years. The unmet needs of the disease, such as pruritus, sleep quality
7 impairment and eczematous skin lesions, have undergone a therapeutic revolution
8 following the commercialisation of drugs such as Janus Kinase (JAK) inhibitors.
9 Upadacitinib, a selective JAK1 inhibitor, has been positioned by both clinical trial results
10 and those published in real clinical practice as the fastest and most effective drug in both
11 reducing pruritus and reducing EASI and vIGA. Although the safety profile may be
12 initially alarming, it is advisable to update the actual data in this regard for proper
13 management. New perspectives for upadacitinib in non-atopic comorbidities such as
14 psoriasis or alopecia areata are beginning to be described, and interest is growing to learn
15 more about its peculiarities

16
17 Plain Language Summary

18 Atopic dermatitis is the most common inflammatory skin disease, the inflammation
19 happens when the body's defence system attacks its own tissue. People with Atopic
20 dermatitis often have itching, red and scaly parts of the skin, the inflammation tends to
21 be long-lasting and repeatedly comes back. The main goal of treatment is to control
22 inflammation which occurs due to a certain group of proteins called cytokines. Receptors
23 called Janus Kinases are involved in the inflammation that happens through cytokines,
24 so they play an important role in this disease. A medicine called Upadacitinib has been
25 approved for the treatment of moderate-severe atopic dermatitis. In this paper you will
26 find the most relevant published information on this drug, including how effective and
27 safe the medicine is in both clinical studies and real-life cases.

28
29 Key words: atopic dermatitis, Janus Kinase inhibitors, upadacitinib, clinical trials, real
30 world evidence, efficacy, safety, psoriasis, alopecia areata

1 INTRODUCTION

2 Atopic dermatitis (AD) is an inflammatory disease that causes itching and eczema. Its
3 prevalence has been increasing in recent decades and is currently estimated at between
4 15-20% of children and up to 7% of adults, with differences between countries [1].
5 Fortunately, most cases are considered mild, although there is a significant percentage of
6 moderate or severe cases where the impact on the lives of patients is very high [2]. In
7 these cases, the approach to the disease is a real therapeutic challenge. Until recently,
8 there were few approved treatments for AD. In 2017, the FDA approved Dupilumab as
9 the first IL-4/13 inhibitor to treat AD. Recently, tralokinumab, a selective IL-13 inhibitor,
10 as well as 3 oral Janus Kinase inhibitors (iJAK), abrocitinib, baricitinib, and upadacitinib
11 (UPA), have been approved [3]. The objective of this review is to present the
12 pharmacological characteristics, clinical results and safety of the development of UPA,
13 as well as the first real practice studies in the treatment of patients with atopic dermatitis.
14

15 PHARMACOLOGY AND PHARMACOKINETICS

16 Like the rest of iJAK, UPA (ABT-494, Rinvoq, Abbvie) is considered a small molecule
17 (those substances that have a molecular weight less than 900 daltons). Specifically, the
18 weight of UPA is 380.4 Daltons. Its molecular formula is C₁₇H₁₉F₃N₆O [4]. UPA is a
19 selective and reversible inhibitor of JAK1. In different in vivo assays, UPA demonstrated
20 approximately 60-fold selectivity for JAK1 over JAK2, 130 times for JAK1 over JAK3,
21 and about 190 times for JAK1 over TYK2 [5]. Atopic dermatitis is mediated by
22 proinflammatory cytokines (including IL-4, IL-13, IL-22, TSLP, IL-31, and IFN- γ) that
23 transduce signals through the JAK1 pathway. JAK1 inhibition with UPA reduces the
24 signaling of many mediators that control the signs and symptoms of atopic dermatitis,
25 such as eczematous skin lesions and pruritus [6]. UPA is well absorbed orally. The
26 average absorption time of UPA tablets is 2-4 hours, with stable plasma concentration
27 reached 4 days after initiation of treatment [7]. Excretion of the drug is mainly via faeces
28 (53%), where 38% of excretion is unchanged UPA. Thirty-four percent of UPA is
29 excreted in the urine, where 24% was unchanged drug. Thirty-four percent of UPA is
30 excreted as metabolites [8], mainly by monooxidation and glucuronidation [4]. The drug
31 is 52% bound to plasma proteins with a blood/plasma ratio of 1. UPA has a short half-life
32 of 9-14 hours [9], with 90% elimination of the drug observed within 24 hours [8].
33 Metabolism of UPA is mediated by CYP3A4, with a possible minor contribution from
34 CYP2D6 [10]. Ketoconazole, itraconazole, posaconazole, voriconazole, clarithromycin

1 and grapefruit would show interaction by CYP3A4 increasing the drug dose, while
2 rifampicin and phenytoin metabolised by the same pathway would decrease the
3 therapeutic effect.

4 Methotrexate showed no effect on UPA plasma exposure [11]. No difference was
5 observed between administration with or without food [10]. Although the UPA
6 pharmacokinetics demonstrated small significant differences in exposure based on
7 indication (rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, axial spondyloarthritis, atopic
8 dermatitis, and ulcerative colitis) and other covariates (age, sex, body weight, race, and
9 ethnicity), no clinically meaningful disease-related differences were reported [7]. UPA
10 pharmacokinetics and steady-state concentrations are similar in adults and adolescents
11 to 17 years of age with atopic dermatitis.

13 SHORT-TERM EFFICACY OF UPA

14 Study NCT02925117 (phase II) examined the therapeutic effect of varying doses of UPA
15 (7.5, 15 and 30 mg) daily in 167 patients with moderate to severe AD [12]. A reduction
16 in EASI of 39%, 62%, and 74% was reported for the 7.5, 15 and 30 mg doses,
17 respectively. The placebo group showed a 23% reduction. Half of the patients receiving
18 UPA 30 mg achieved EASI90, demonstrating a clear dose-response relationship [12].
19 The response obtained at week 4 was maintained until week 16. Thirty-one per cent of
20 patients in the UPA 15 mg group and 50% of patients treated with 30 mg achieved a vIGA
21 0-1. With regard to pruritus reduction, a decrease of -31.4% was observed after the first
22 week of treatment, with a reduction of -66.9% reported at week 16 [13].

23 In Measure Up 1, Measure Up 2, and AD Up, all of which are phase III trials, a
24 significantly higher percentage ($p < 0.001$) of patients treated with UPA 30 mg/15 mg
25 achieved an EASI 90 response (66% and 53%; 58% and 42%; 63% and 43%) vs. placebo
26 (8%, 5% and 13%) at week 16 [14]. These results were statistically significant at week
27 12. Furthermore, with both doses of UPA, 30 mg and 15 mg, relevant reduction in pruritus
28 was observed significantly ($p \leq 0.001$) vs placebo from first week and it was maintained
29 until week 16 ($p \leq 0.001$).

30 In Measure Up 1 and Measure Up 2 trials, just one day after the first dose (Day 2),
31 clinically significant reductions in itch were observed in patients receiving UPA 30 mg
32 vs placebo ($p < 0.001$). While, patients receiving UPA 15 mg experienced a reduction in
33 itching at day 3 ($p < 0.001$). A clinically relevant reduction in itch was defined as an
34 improvement on the itch numerical rating scale (NRS) ≥ 4 .

36 LONG-TERM EFFICACY OF UPA

37 Patients with more significant forms of atopic dermatitis (AD) will require long-term
38 treatment, so efficacy data beyond week 16 are needed to make appropriate clinical

1 decisions. Long-term efficacy data for UPA in the management of moderate-severe AD
2 are mainly based on the results of 3 randomized clinical trials (RCTs): AD Up [15] and
3 two more recently published Measure Up 1 and Measure Up 2 [16]. These last two are
4 multicenter, double-blind, phase 3, placebo-controlled studies that included a total of
5 1609 patients (adults and adolescents). In follow-up data analysis, once-daily UPA (15
6 mg or 30 mg) provided durable efficacy with responses maintained through 52 weeks of
7 treatment [16]. It should be pointed out that the patients who started treatment with UPA
8 15 mg on day 1 had slightly higher efficacy at week 52 than at week 16; whereas those
9 who started treatment with UPA 30 mg on day 1 maintained the demonstrated efficacy at
10 week 16 through week 52. For the more stringent endpoints of EASI90, EASI100, vIGA-
11 AD 0, and WP -NRS 0/1, responses were maintained or improved at week 52 compared
12 to week 16. In addition, in reference to what has been published, it should be noted that
13 patients treated with placebo and rerandomized at week 16 to receive UPA had rates of
14 response up to week 52 similar to those who received UPA from day 1. On the other hand,
15 it is worth mentioning that UPA 15 mg achieved and maintained high levels of efficacy,
16 but there was greater relative benefit with the 30 mg dose, since patients who received
17 UPA 30 mg achieved numerically higher response rates for all measures evaluated until
18 week 52 than those who received UPA 15 mg. Although week 52 results of both trials
19 have been published, these studies are still ongoing and longer-term data will be
20 interesting. In another review article regarding the results of the phase 3 RCTs available
21 for oral iJAK used in patients with AD, they highlight that the efficacy of both UPA dosing
22 regimens is maintained up to week 52 for all the criteria of assessment.

23 On the other hand, comment that of the 3 RCTs that evaluate the use of UPA in the long
24 term in AD, only the AD Up study shows a slight decrease in the efficacy parameters
25 evaluated in the two UPA arms between weeks 16 and 52 [15]. However, Measure Up 1
26 and 2 show greater stability over time in terms of efficacy [16]. Note that in these RCTs
27 the concomitant use of TCS was allowed. In fact, in published systematic reviews and
28 meta-analyses, the best efficacy data (EASI75) at 52 weeks are obtained by UPA 30 mg+
29 TCS, being the main combination that we would use in real clinical practice. The results
30 of the combination of UPA + topical corticosteroids (TCS) in 901 patients (UPA 15 mg
31 + TCS, 297 to UPA 30 mg + TCS, and 304 to PBO + TCS) have recently been published
32 [15]. At week 52, the group of UPA 15 mg + TCS and UPA 30 mg + TCS who achieved
33 vIGA-AD 0/1 reached 33.5% and 45.2%, respectively; and EASI75 were 50.8% and
34 69.0%, respectively. The efficacy obtained at week 16 was maintained at week 52, with

1 no new or serious side effects. Table 1 lists the published or ongoing clinical trials of
2 treatment of atopic dermatitis with UPA.

3 4 NETWORK META-ANALYSES

5 In the publication by Qiu M et al. [17] five efficacy outcomes were considered: Worst
6 Pruritus-Numerical Rating Scale (WP-NRS) at week 1, EASI75 at week 2 and 4, and
7 EASI90, EASI100, vIGA-AD 0-1, as well as WP-NRS all together at week 16. Both,
8 UPA 15 mg and 30 mg showed superiority to placebo in efficacy outcomes. UPA 30 mg
9 showed an EASI75 ratio (RR 1.32, 95% CI 1.18-1.49) at week 2, as well as better results
10 at week 16 in vIGA-AD (RR 1.36, 95% CI 1.24-1.50), EASI90 (RR1.36, 95% CI 1.02-
11 1.80), EASI100 (RR 1.49, 95% CI 1.16-1.90). Regarding pruritus symptom (WP-NRS),
12 the 30 mg dose was also superior at week 16 (RR 1.26, 95% CI 1.11-1.42UPA 30 mg
13 dose was associated with increased risk of SAE (RR 1.10, 95% CI 1.03-1.17), and
14 increased risk of acne (RR 1.55, 95% CI 1.06-2.27).

15 Another recent bayesian network meta-analysis review [18] (PROSPERO
16 CRD42022329007) analysed the safety of different iJAK. They included 5 clinical trials
17 with UPA, all of which were compared with placebo except one that was compared with
18 dupilumab. The study showed an increased risk of any AEs with UPA with an Odds Ratio
19 (OR) of 1.46 (95% CI, 1.19-1.81). Regarding the risk of any infection, an OR of 1.67
20 (95% CI, 1.19-2.43) was concluded. However, no differences were found between the
21 different iJAK when analysing the risk of serious infections. The risk of herpes zoster is
22 higher with UPA when compared to dupilumab. In terms of cardiovascular adverse
23 events, UPA has only recorded three events, compared to other drugs such as abrocitinib,
24 which has recorded 23. The 2022 meta-analysis [19] analysed the efficacy and safety of
25 the 3 marketed iJAK, including UPA. It concluded that the 30 mg dose of upadacitinib
26 was more effective than any other JAKi regimen by both EIAS75 and IGA 0/1. The 15
27 mg group was also superior to all but abrocitinib 200 mg. Another finding was that the
28 UPA 30 mg dose was associated with an increased risk of emerging adverse effects
29 (EAEs) with an OR of 1.48 (95% CI, 1.02-2.27) compared to all other JAKi. Subgroup
30 analysis revealed an elevated risk of TEAEs with UPA 30 mg with an OR of 6.71 (95%
31 CI, 1.48-30.83). The systematic review published by Silverberg et al. [20] concluded that
32 UPA 30 mg at 16 weeks achieved EASI50 in 84% of patients, although it was not
33 statistically superior to abrocitinib 200 mg. EASI75 was achieved in 70% of patients, and
34 EASI90 in 52%. The IGA response for UPA was not analysed. A year later, the same

1 author published a new meta-analysis [21] where he again concluded that UPA 30 mg and
2 15 mg were the most effective molecules in the short term (12 to 16 weeks) in the
3 treatment of atopic dermatitis. Focus in vIGA-AD, UPA 30 mg was statistically more
4 effective than the other molecules tested. In terms of speed of action, UPA 30 mg
5 continues to be the molecule with the best EASI75 results at week 2. The AD Up study
6 of upadacitinib was not included in this analysis. Ayen-Rodríguez et al. performed the
7 52-week analysis [22], concluding that UPA 30 mg maintained the position of best
8 molecule, achieving EASI75 in 84.7% (95% CI 77.3-92.1), improving slightly (84.9%,
9 CI 80.3-89.5) when concomitant use of topical corticosteroids is analysed. Drucker et al
10 [23] published a living systematic review and network meta-analysis (PROSPERO
11 CRD42018088112) where they concluded that UPA 30 mg and abrocitinib 200 mg were
12 the molecules with the best efficacy results, and that UPA 15 mg showed a response
13 similar to that observed with dupilumab. Zhang et al. [24] republished the analysis of all
14 JAKi, both oral and topical. Once again, UPA 30 mg showed the best efficacy ranking in
15 the 16-week forest plot analysis.

16

17 REAL WORLD EVIDENCE

18 Once the main characteristics of efficacy and safety of the different clinical trials that
19 have allowed the approval of UPA in the management of moderate-severe AD have been
20 commented, it is pertinent to verify if these data are replicated in real clinical practice. In
21 our daily clinical activity, patients differ substantially from those included in clinical trials
22 that have much stricter inclusion criteria. In all the reported series, the use of topical
23 corticosteroids or associated immunosuppressants have been allowed at the discretion of
24 the prescribing physician.

25 Vanlerberghe [25] included AD patients from 18 French centers in his study, 54 of them
26 treated with the 15 mg dose and 12 with the 30 mg dose. Approximately $\frac{3}{4}$ of the patients
27 had received cyclosporine and dupilumab and more than half had received at least three
28 systemic/biological treatments. Efficacy outcomes were measured at 12 and 24 weeks. In
29 relation to the 15 mg dose, 37.5% of the patients reached the IGA 0/1 proposed as the
30 main measure of efficacy at 6 months, while with the 30 mg dose it was reached by 75%
31 (n=3). From a safety point of view, the most commonly reported adverse effect was
32 elevation of cholesterol and triglyceride levels with no communication of
33 thromboembolic effects. In relation to survival, it is noteworthy that treatment with UPA
34 15 mg was discontinued in at least 9 patients.

1 Pereyra-Rodriguez et al. report the efficacy and safety results in the short term (16 weeks)
2 [26] and long term (52 weeks) [27]. In this Spanish multicentre study, patients from 16
3 hospitals from all over the Spanish national territory were included. Forty three patients
4 were included in the short-term study (90.7% had previously received treatment with
5 ciclosporin and 74.4% dupilumab). UPA 30 mg was prescribed at the 60.4% of patients.
6 The high baseline EASI value (24.9 ± 9.6) and impact on quality of life (DLQI 17.4 ± 6.8)
7 stood out. At 16 weeks the mean EASI decreased to 4.1 ± 4.6 (83.5% improvement;
8 $p < 0.0001$ and 62.8% showed IGA 0/1 at the end of the follow-up period. 76.7% of
9 patients achieved EASI75 at w16 regarding both posologies. Only one patient
10 discontinued treatment, in this case for safety reasons. The data at 52 weeks, however,
11 have only been obtained in 22 patients of the previously mentioned cohort. In this case
12 and without communicating discordant efficacy and safety data with short-term data, it
13 should be noted that the probability of survival of the drug was 77.3%, without observing
14 differences because of dose, sex, or previous treatments.

15 Hagino [28] presents a retrospective series of 31 patients with moderate-severe AD. The
16 short-term efficacy evaluation shows a reduction of 85.6% in EASI at 12 weeks and
17 81.3% in AD control tool (ADCT). Multivariate linear regression analysis revealed that
18 high percent reduction of EASI at week 12 was associated with high baseline eosinophil
19 count or female gender. No adverse effects other than those already described were
20 reported in clinical trials.

21 The series presented by Dal Bello [29] communicates a lower number of patients than
22 those previously mentioned with only 10 patients. The authors point out that all of them
23 had been refractory to treatment with Dupilumab and 90% of them, possibly due to safety
24 conditions and comorbidities not reported in the manuscript, received the 15 mg dose.
25 UPA showed a rapid efficacy in all the patients, who reached EASI75 within 4 weeks and
26 more pronounced improvement at 8 weeks, with a mean reduction of EASI from 28.7 to
27 1.7 at the end of the study period. No additional safety findings were reported. The
28 decrease in the NRS pruritus score and the quality of life values measured by DLQI
29 showed an evaluation in parallel with the decrease in the EASI.

30 Chiricozzi et al [30] published a prospective study in real clinical practice of 43 patients
31 under treatment with UPA during 16 weeks of treatment and follow-up. It was reported
32 that 97.5%, 82.1% and 69.2% of patients achieved an EASI75, EASI 90 and EASI 100,

1 respectively. Patients who did not respond to dupilumab were included, where UPA
2 showed a successful response in these patients.

3 Finally, Feraru et al [31] report a series of 12 patients in a retrospective study of 4 hospital
4 centers in Israel, whose access had been through the expanded access program. The initial
5 dosage in all patients was 15 mg/day. However, in 7 out of 12 patients, the dosage was
6 raised to 30 mg/day due to a partial response. 3 patients discontinued treatment due to
7 lack of efficacy and in 2 of them the cessation occurred upon reaching the therapeutic
8 objective (IGA 0/1), which was lost after its suspension. The reintroduction of the
9 medication produced the extent of the previous response reached.

10 New RWE experience with this iJAK in 38 Italian patients has recently been published
11 [32]. More than half of the patients previously received dupilumab. Upa 15 mg dose was
12 prescribed in 12 patients, while 26 patients received the 30 mg dose. Of the total patients,
13 92.11% had an EASI ≤ 7 , 97.14% at week 16. Sixty percent of patients showed an
14 EASI100. None of the 13 adverse events were serious, nor was discontinuation of the
15 drug. These results mirror the data published in clinical trials or NMA, and even improve
16 on them in difficult-to-control patients such as those who have not responded adequately
17 to dupilumab.

18 Kiefer S et al [32] published this year the results observed in a paediatric and adolescent
19 population diagnosed with moderate-to-severe AD with upadacitinib. A total of 23
20 patients have been presented, seven of them treated with UPA and the rest with
21 dupilumab. Both drugs showed an improvement in all the parameters studied (EASI,
22 VAS-itch, CDLQI, POEM and DFIQ), with no significant differences between them.

23 On the other hand, non-atopic comorbidities in patients with AD are becoming
24 increasingly important in therapeutic decisions. Psoriasis and AD may be present in the
25 same patient. In the article published by Gargiulo L et al [33], a series of four patients
26 with overlapping psoriasis and AD successfully treated with UPA 15 mg (3 patients) and
27 30 mg (1 patient) is presented. Although the overlap of these skin diseases is rare, UPA
28 could be positioned as first line in these cases. In the last two years, cases of alopecia
29 areata successfully treated with UPA [34], a disease related to AD, have been published.

30

31 SAFETY

32 Regarding drug safety, the adverse effects (AEs) described were similar to those seen in
33 patients with rheumatoid arthritis who have used the drug. No serious events such as of
34 death, adjudicated MACE, lymphoma, active TB, adjudicated GI perforations, or renal

1 dysfunction reported in any treatment group were observed from Measure Up 1 and 2
2 [14]. When we evaluated these adverse effects at week 16, the most frequent were acne
3 (most of which were mild or moderate), upper respiratory tract infections,
4 nasopharyngitis, headaches, and increased blood CPK. If we assess, the adverse events
5 of special interest stand out infections (including herpes zoster) and alterations in the
6 complete blood count, especially neutropenia (mostly transient), but also anemia and
7 leukopenia. At 52 weeks the safety profile is similar to that observed at week 16 [16]. The
8 rate of treatment discontinuations due to AEs was low overall, though higher in the UPA
9 30 mg group vs the 15 mg group through week 52. Most events were nonserious. The
10 acnes that appeared were managed with topical products or without intervention.
11 Regarding serious infections, the most frequent were pneumonia and eczema herpeticum.
12 The most frequent opportunistic infections (excluding herpes zoster and tuberculosis)
13 were eczema herpeticum and Kaposi variceliform eruption, observing 2 cases of
14 tuberculosis. Patients treated with UPA 30 mg reported elevated transaminases and CPK,
15 hematologic abnormalities (anemia, lymphopenia) more frequently compared to UPA 15
16 mg. The analytical alterations were transient, not serious, and reported in the first 12
17 weeks of exposure to the drug. Treatment discontinuation due to analytical adverse events
18 was infrequent. One uncontrolled hypertensive patient treated with UPA 15 mg suffered
19 a non-fatal stroke, which was not related to the drug. One patient with a personal history
20 of deep vein thrombosis presented a new episode taking UPA 15 mg, and a second patient
21 suffered a pulmonary thromboembolism taking UPA 30 mg and in the context of a
22 COVID-19 infection. Both were unrelated to the drug by the investigator group.

23 In the AD Up study, where both UPA doses are used in combination with TCS were well
24 tolerated in the overall population during the double-blind period and at the 52-week
25 análisis [15]. No new safety signals were observed compared with the safety profile in the
26 UPA use in the Measure Up 1 and 2.

27 Through week 16, there were no events of death, active TB, lymphoma, adjudicated GI
28 perforation, adjudicated VTE, adjudicated MACE, or grade 3 or 4 thrombocytopenia
29 reported in any treatment group. One event of arterial thrombosis was reported for a
30 patient in the placebo plus topical corticosteroids group. Serious AEs and incidence of
31 AEs leading to discontinuation of study drug were similar among all treatment groups.

32 At week 16, the most prominent AEs were again acne, nasopharyngitis, upper respiratory
33 tract infection, oral herpes, headaches, and elevated CPK blood levels [35]. Through week
34 52, the exposure-adjusted event rates of serious AEs and AEs leading to discontinuation

1 were similar between UPA 15 mg plus TCS and UPA 30 mg plus TCS. The most
2 frequently reported TEAEs through week 52 were acne, nasopharyngitis, blood CPK
3 increase, atopic dermatitis, and upper respiratory tract infection. There were no reports of
4 death, active TB, lymphoma, or adjudicated GI perforation through 52 weeks. The only
5 highlights of this period were 2 MACEs (defined as CV death, nonfatal MI, and nonfatal
6 stroke) reported in a 60-year old UPA 15 mg + TCS-treated patient (nonfatal
7 subarachnoid hemorrhage) and a 69-year old UPA 30 mg + TCS-treated patient (nonfatal
8 stroke). Both patients were unrelated to study drug with CV risk factors. One adjudicated
9 Venous Tromboembolism was reported for a 66-year old white male patient with a history
10 of obesity and hypercholesterolemia in the UPA 15 mg + TCS group. The event was
11 deemed not serious and possibly related to study drug by the study physician and the
12 patient was withdrawn from the study.

13 The latest safety analysis of UPA, including patients with rheumatoid arthritis, psoriatic
14 arthritis, and atopic dermatitis, in a total of 6991 patients (representing 15 425 PY of
15 exposure (maximum duration 2.75-5.45 years) has been published in 2023 [36]. The rates
16 of any TSEA leading to drug discontinuation were similar in all diseases. Patients with
17 rheumatoid arthritis and psoriatic arthritis showed more severe adverse events than those
18 observed in patients with AD. Rates of herpes zoster (1.6-3.6), non-melanoma skin cancer
19 (0-0.8) were higher than active comparators in clinical trials in rheumatoid arthritis and
20 psoriatic arthritis. Patients with AD showed higher rates of acne, however, major
21 cardiovascular events, venous thromboembolism, and malignancies were all less frequent
22 compared to the RA and PsA population. The conclusion of the study, and one that should
23 be considered in routine clinical practice, is that patient profile may determine the
24 frequency of adverse events, and that it may not be possible to extrapolate observations
25 from the RA and PsA patients to the AD population.

26

27 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE VISION

28 Oral JAK inhibitors, mainly JAK1, have been shown to be effective and have an
29 acceptable safety profile for both short- and long-term treatment in patients with atopic
30 dermatitis. UPA has been shown to maintain the same, and in some studies even improve,
31 therapeutic response reported in clinical trials. The drug development plan has been
32 important with a large number of patients with moderate-to-severe AD, which has
33 allowed the advantages of the drug, as well as the most frequent adverse events, to be
34 understood. Currently, the upadacitinib development plan has 9 projects, which are listed

1 in table 2. The experience in clinical practice is quite positive, with rapid control of
2 pruritus, and a very significant reduction in EASI and vIGA scores, with more than half
3 of the patients showing complete control of the disease. During the first stage of the drug's
4 use in clinical practice, there was some apprehension about the long-term duration of
5 response. As demonstrated, the results are significantly maintained, with no increase in
6 the rate of adverse effects, as well as a low rate of permanent discontinuations of APU.
7 These characteristics make it an interesting option in patients with AD. The risk of
8 herpetic infection, associated with a higher severity of AD (vIGA 3 or 4), mainly due to
9 eczema herpeticum, needs to be taken into account, and whether it would be appropriate
10 to instruct the patient to take antiviral treatment in case of the occurrence of this infectious
11 complication. Although the shadow that haunts all iJAK remains on the table, it is true
12 that each of them has a slightly different side-effect profile, but one that is acceptable to
13 the clinician. The most important thing is to avoid prescribing in patients with risk factors,
14 where the monoclonal antibodies may offer greater reassurance from that point of view.
15 The use of iJAK is likely to grow significantly in the coming years. Targeting non-atopic
16 comorbidities, such as alopecia areata, inflammatory bowel disease, and even allergic
17 contact dermatitis, is of particular interest because they are associated with complex
18 patient management, which may also be resistant to standard treatments. JAK signalling
19 plays an important role in many diseases, including autoimmune diseases, where UPA is
20 likely to be positioned as the first line of treatment in these patients. Efficacy and safety
21 studies in children will expand the therapeutic arsenal in this special age group.
22 In conclusion, upadacitinib is an oral iJAK indicated for the treatment of moderate-to-
23 severe atopic dermatitis, which has been shown to achieve significant results both in
24 clinical trials and in real clinical practice experience, with an acceptable safety profile.

25
26

27 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- 28 • UPA has positioned itself as one of the most important drugs in the treatment of
29 atopic dermatitis, mainly by positioning itself as the drug with the best efficacy
30 and safety profile.
- 31 • After the results observed in the Measure Up 1 and 2 clinical trials, achieving an
32 EASI75 in up to 74% of patients, the results observed at 52 weeks have shown a
33 similar response to that obtained at week 16, with no new or different long-term
34 adverse events.

- 1 • The 30 mg dose has been shown to be superior to the 15 mg dose in all primary
2 and secondary endpoints, with a modest increase in adverse events, although not
3 related to the severity of adverse events.
- 4 • The profile of patients with atopic dermatitis has been shown to have a lower rate
5 of severe events than patients with rheumatoid arthritis or psoriatic arthritis. The
6 reduction in pruritus is a key feature of the drug's characteristics.
- 7 • UPA is a suitable drug for the treatment of atopic dermatitis in the adolescent
8 population and beyond, although patient monitoring during follow-up and
9 treatment is necessary, as well as consideration of risk factors for infections and/or
10 oncological risk according to the patient's age and personal and family history.
- 11 • The coexistence of atopic dermatitis and autoimmune diseases such as
12 inflammatory bowel disease may position upadacitinib as a first-line therapy in
13 the future.
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17

1 REFERENCES

- 2 1. Chiesa Fuxench ZC, Block JK, Boguniewicz M, Boyle J, Fonacier L, Gelfand JM,
3 Grayson MH, Margolis DJ, Mitchell L, Silverberg JI, Schwartz L, Simpson EL,
4 Ong PY. Atopic Dermatitis in America Study: A Cross-Sectional Study
5 Examining the Prevalence and Disease Burden of Atopic Dermatitis in the US
6 Adult Population. *J Invest Dermatol.* 2019;139(3):583-590.
- 7 2. Silverberg JI. Selected comorbidities of atopic dermatitis: Atopy,
8 neuropsychiatric, and musculoskeletal disorders. *Clin Dermatol.* 2017;35(4):360-
9 366
- 10 3. Dodson J, Lio PA. Biologics and Small Molecule Inhibitors: an Update in
11 Therapies for Allergic and Immunologic Skin Diseases. *Curr Allergy Asthma*
12 *Rep.* 2022;22(12):183-193.
- 13 4. National Center for Biotechnology Information (2022). PubChem compound
14 summary for CID 58557659 [Internet]. [cited 2022 Nov 10]. Available from:
15 <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/compound/Upadacitinib>
- 16 5. Parmentier JM, Voss J, Graff C, Schwartz A, Argiriadi M, Friedman M, Camp
17 HS, Padley RJ, George JS, Hyland D, Rosebraugh M, Wishart N, Olson L, Long
18 AJ. In vitro and in vivo characterization of the JAK1 selectivity of upadacitinib
19 (ABT-494). *BMC Rheumatol.* 2018;2:23.
- 20 6. Bao L, Zhang H, Chan LS. The involvement of the JAK-STAT signaling pathway
21 in chronic inflammatory skin disease atopic dermatitis. *JAKSTAT.*
22 2013;2(3):e24137.
- 23 7. Nader A, Stodtmann S, Friedel A, Mohamed MF, Othman AA. Pharmacokinetics
24 of Upadacitinib in Healthy Subjects and Subjects With Rheumatoid Arthritis,
25 Crohn's Disease, Ulcerative Colitis, or Atopic Dermatitis: Population Analyses of
26 Phase 1 and 2 Clinical Trials. *J Clin Pharmacol.* 2020;60(4):528-539.
- 27 8. Klünder B, Mittapalli RK, Mohamed MF, Friedel A, Noertersheuser P, Othman
28 AA. Population Pharmacokinetics of Upadacitinib Using the Immediate-Release
29 and Extended-Release Formulations in Healthy Subjects and Subjects with
30 Rheumatoid Arthritis: Analyses of Phase I-III Clinical Trials. *Clin*
31 *Pharmacokinet.* 2019;58(8):1045-1058.
- 32 9. Mohamed MF, Trueman S, Feng T, Friedman A, Othman AA. The JAK1 Inhibitor
33 Upadacitinib Has No Effect on the Pharmacokinetics of Levonorgestrel and
34 Ethinylestradiol: A Study in Healthy Female Subjects. *J Clin Pharmacol.*

- 1 2019;59(4):510-516.
- 2 10. Mohamed MF, Jungerwirth S, Asatryan A, Jiang P, Othman AA. Assessment of
3 effect of CYP3A inhibition, CYP induction, OATP1B inhibition, and high-fat
4 meal on pharmacokinetics of the JAK1 inhibitor upadacitinib. *Br J Clin*
5 *Pharmacol.* 2017;83(10):2242-2248.
- 6 11. Mohamed MF, Camp HS, Jiang P, Padley RJ, Asatryan A, Othman AA.
7 Pharmacokinetics, Safety and Tolerability of ABT-494, a Novel Selective JAK 1
8 Inhibitor, in Healthy Volunteers and Subjects with Rheumatoid Arthritis. *Clin*
9 *Pharmacokinet.* 2016;55(12):1547-1558.
- 10 12. Guttman-Yassky E, Thaçi D, Pangan AL, Hong HC, Papp KA, Reich K, Beck
11 LA, Mohamed MF, Othman AA, Anderson JK, Gu Y, Teixeira HD, Silverberg JI.
12 Upadacitinib in adults with moderate to severe atopic dermatitis: 16-week results
13 from a randomized, placebo-controlled trial. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.*
14 2020;145(3):877-884.
- 15 13. Blauvelt, A.; Teixeira, H.D.; Simpson, E.L.; Costanzo, A.; De Bruin-Weller, M.;
16 Barbarot, S.; Prajapati, V.H.; Lio, P.; Hu, X.; Wu, T.; et al. Efficacy and Safety of
17 Upadacitinib vs Dupilumab in Adults with Moderate-to-Severe Atopic
18 Dermatitis: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2021;157:1047–
19 1055.
- 20 14. Guttman-Yassky E, Teixeira HD, Simpson EL, Papp KA, Pangan AL, Blauvelt
21 A, Thaçi D, Chu CY, Hong HC, Katoh N, Paller AS, Calimlim B, Gu Y, Hu X,
22 Liu M, Yang Y, Liu J, Tenorio AR, Chu AD, Irvine AD. Once-daily upadacitinib
23 versus placebo in adolescents and adults with moderate-to-severe atopic
24 dermatitis (Measure Up 1 and Measure Up 2): results from two replicate double-
25 blind, randomised controlled phase 3 trials. *Lancet.* 2021;397:2151-2168.
- 26 15. Silverberg JI, de Bruin-Weller M, Bieber T, Soong W, Kabashima K, Costanzo
27 A, Rosmarin D, Lynde C, Liu J, Gamelli A, Zeng J, Ladizinski B, Chu AD, Reich
28 K. Upadacitinib plus topical corticosteroids in atopic dermatitis: Week 52 AD Up
29 study results. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 2022;149:977-987.
- 30 16. Simpson EL, Papp KA, Blauvelt A, Chu CY, Hong HC, Katoh N, Calimlim BM,
31 Thyssen JP, Chiou AS, Bissonnette R, Stein Gold LF, Wegzyn C, Hu X, Liu M,
32 Liu J, Tenorio AR, Chu AD, Guttman-Yassky E. Efficacy and Safety of
33 Upadacitinib in Patients With Moderate to Severe Atopic Dermatitis: Analysis of
34 Follow-up Data From the Measure Up 1 and Measure Up 2 Randomized Clinical

- 1 Trials. *JAMA Dermatol.* 2022;158(4):404-413.
- 2 17. Qiu M, Duan XY, Yin DG. Network meta-analysis on the efficacy and safety of
3 upadacitinib in adolescents and adults with moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis.
4 *Int J Dermatol.* 2022;61(1):e24-e26
- 5 18. Alves C, Penedones A, Mendes D, Batel Marques F. The safety of systemic Janus
6 kinase inhibitors in atopic dermatitis: a systematic review and network meta-
7 analysis. *Eur J Clin Pharmacol.* 2022;78(12):1923-1933
- 8 19. Wan H, Jia H, Xia T, Zhang D. Comparative efficacy and safety of abrocitinib,
9 baricitinib, and upadacitinib for moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis: A network
10 meta-analysis. *Dermatol Ther.* 2022;35(9):e15636.
- 11 20. Silverberg JI, Thyssen JP, Fahrbach K, Mickle K, Cappelleri JC, Romero W,
12 Cameron MC, Myers DE, Clibborn C, DiBonaventura M. Comparative efficacy
13 and safety of systemic therapies used in moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis: a
14 systematic literature review and network meta-analysis. *J Eur Acad Dermatol*
15 *Venereol.* 2021;35(9):1797-1810
- 16 21. Silverberg JI, Hong HC, Thyssen JP, Calimlim BM, Joshi A, Teixeira HD, Collins
17 EB, Crowell MM, Johnson SJ, Armstrong AW. Comparative Efficacy of Targeted
18 Systemic Therapies for Moderate to Severe Atopic Dermatitis without Topical
19 Corticosteroids: Systematic Review and Network Meta-analysis. *Dermatol Ther*
20 *(Heidelb).* 2022;12(5):1181-1196
- 21 22. Ayen-Rodríguez A, Pereyra-Rodríguez JJ, Navarro-Triviño FJ, Alcantara-Luna
22 S, Domínguez-Cruz J, Galán-Gutiérrez M, Vilar-Palomo S, Armario-Hita JC,
23 Ruiz-Villaverde R. Long-Term Effectiveness and Safety of Biologic and Small
24 Molecule Drugs for Moderate to Severe Atopic Dermatitis: A Systematic Review.
25 *Life (Basel).* 2022;12(8):1159
- 26 23. Drucker AM, Morra DE, Prieto-Merino D, Ellis AG, Yiu ZZN, Rochweg B, Di
27 Giorgio S, Arents BWM, Burton T, Spuls PI, Schmitt J, Flohr C. Systemic
28 Immunomodulatory Treatments for Atopic Dermatitis: Update of a Living
29 Systematic Review and Network Meta-analysis. *JAMA Dermatol.*
30 2022;158(5):523-532
- 31 24. Zhang L, Wang L, Jiang X. The efficacy of Janus kinase inhibitors in patients with
32 atopic dermatitis: A systematic review and network meta-analysis. *Dermatol*
33 *Ther.* 2021;34(5):e15098
- 34 25. Vanlerberghe J, Dezoteux F, Martin C, Jachiet M, Soria A, Tétart F, Modeste-

- 1 Duval AB, Bursztejn AC, Misery L, Aubin F, Lasek A, Leleu C, Du-Thanh A,
2 Pasteur J, Pralong P, Nosbaum A, Droitcourt C, Viguier M, Tauber M, Seneschal
3 J, Barbarot S, Staumont-Sallé D. Effectiveness and tolerance of Janus kinase
4 inhibitors for the treatment of recalcitrant atopic dermatitis in a real-life French
5 multicenter adult cohort. *J Am Acad Dermatol*. 2022:S0190-9622(22)02960-7.
- 6 26. Pereyra-Rodriguez JJ, Herranz P, Figueras-Nart I, Perez B, Elosua M, Munera-
7 Campos M, Melgosa-Ramos J, Zaragoza V, Silvestre JF, Campos-Domínguez M,
8 Guilabert A, Miquel J, Alcantara-Luna S, de la Cueva P, Serra-Baldrich E,
9 Armario-Hita JC. Treatment of severe atopic dermatitis with upadacitinib in real
10 clinical practice. Short-term efficacy and safety results. *J Investig Allergol Clin*
11 *Immunol*. 2022 Jun 2:0. Epub ahead of print.
- 12 27. Pereyra-Rodriguez JJ, Herranz P, Figuras-Nart I, Perez B, Elosua M, Munera-
13 Campos M, Melgosa-Ramos J, Zaragoza Ninet V, Silvestre JF, Campos-
14 Domínguez M, Guilabert A, Miquel J, Alcantara-Luna S, de la Cueva P, Serra-
15 Baldrich E, Armario-Hita JC. Upadacitinib for the Treatment of Atopic Dermatitis
16 in a Spanish Cohort-Real Life: Fifty-Two-Week Follow-up Results. *Dermatitis*.
17 2022;33(6S):S124-S127.
- 18 28. Hagino T, Saeki H, Kanda N. The efficacy and safety of upadacitinib treatment
19 for moderate to severe atopic dermatitis in real-world practice in Japan. *J*
20 *Dermatol*. 2022;49:1158–1167.
- 21 29. Dal Bello G, Schena D, Girolomoni G. Upadacitinib in patients with resistant
22 atopic dermatitis: a retrospective case-series. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*.
23 2022;36(9):1499-1500.
- 24 30. Chiricozzi A, Gori N, Narcisi A, et al. Effectiveness and safety of upadacitinib in
25 the treatment of moderate-severe atopic dermatitis: a multicentric, prospective,
26 real-world, cohort study. *Drugs R D*. 2022;3:1–8.
- 27 31. Feraru G, Nevet MJ, Samuelov L, Hodak E, Avitan-Hersh E, Ziv M, Dodiuk-Gad
28 RP. Real-life experience of upadacitinib for the treatment of adult patients with
29 moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis - a case series. *J Eur Acad Dermatol*
30 *Venereol*. 2022;36(10):e832-e833
- 31 32. Kiefer S, König A, Gerger V, Rummenigge C, Müller AC, Jung T, Frank A,
32 Tassopoulos G, Laurent E, Kaufmann R, Pinter A. Efficacy and Treatment
33 Satisfaction of Different Systemic Therapies in Children and Adolescents with

1 Moderate-to-Severe Atopic Dermatitis: A Real-World Study. *J Clin Med.*
2 2023;12(3):1175.

3 33. Gargiulo L, Ibba L, Pavia G, Avagliano J, Cortese A, Costanzo A, Narcisi A.
4 Upadacitinib for the treatment of concomitant psoriasis and atopic dermatitis: a
5 case series. *J Dermatolog Treat.* 2023;34(1):2183729.

6 34. Youssef S, Bordone LA. Effective treatment of alopecia universalis with oral
7 upadacitinib. *JAAD Case Rep.* 2022 Aug 19;31:80-82.

8 35. Napolitano M, Potestio L, Hansel K, Marietti R, Piscitelli I, Fabbrocini G,
9 Stingeni L, Patrino C. Efficacy and safety of upadacitinib in adult patients
10 affected by moderate to severe atopic dermatitis: a 16-week real-life dual-centre
11 experience. *Clin Exp Dermatol.* 2022 Nov 14;llac078.

12 36. Burmester GR, Cohen SB, Winthrop KL, Nash P, Irvine AD, Deodhar A, Mysler
13 E, Tanaka Y, Liu J, Lacerda AP, Palac H, Shaw T, Mease PJ, Guttman-Yassky E.
14 Safety profile of upadacitinib over 15 000 patient-years across rheumatoid
15 arthritis, psoriatic arthritis, ankylosing spondylitis and atopic dermatitis. *RMD*
16 *Open.* 2023;9(1):e002735.

17 37. Reich K, Teixeira HD, de Bruin-Weller M, Bieber T, Soong W, Kabashima K, et al.
18 Safety and efficacy of upadacitinib in combination with topical corticosteroids in
19 adolescents and adults with moderate-to-severe atopic dermatitis (AD Up):
20 results from a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 3 trial.
21 *Lancet.* 2021;397(10290):2169-2181. Erratum in: *Lancet.* 2021;397(10292):2336.
22 Erratum in: *Lancet.* 202;398(10302):746.

23 38. Katoh N, Ohya Y, Murota H, Ikeda M, Hu X, Ikeda K, et al. Safety and Efficacy of
24 Upadacitinib for Atopic Dermatitis in Japan: 2-Year Interim Results from the Phase
25 3 Rising Up Study. *Dermatol Ther (Heidelb).* 2023;13(1):221-234.

26
27
28 *Dodson J, Lio PA. Biologics and Small Molecule Inhibitors: an Update in
29 Therapies for Allergic and Immunologic Skin Diseases. *Curr Allergy Asthma Rep.*
30 22(12), 183-193 (2022)

31 Must-read article to improve understanding of the differentiating features between
32 biologic and small molecule therapy.

33

1 *Bao L, Zhang H, Chan LS. The involvement of the JAK-STAT signaling pathway
2 in chronic inflammatory skin disease atopic dermatitis. *JAKSTAT*. 2 (3):e24137
3 (2013)

4 Fundamental article to understand the intracellular signalling mechanism of the
5 JAK-STAT pathway and its impact on inflammatory mechanisms that mediate
6 diseases such as atopic dermatitis.

7
8 *Simpson EL, Papp KA, Blauvelt A, Chu CY, Hong HC, Katoh N, et al. Efficacy
9 and Safety of Upadacitinib in Patients With Moderate to Severe Atopic Dermatitis:
10 Analysis of Follow-up Data From the Measure Up 1 and Measure Up 2
11 Randomized Clinical Trials. *JAMA Dermatol*. 158 (4), 404-413 (2022)

12
13 Reporting results of upadacitinib in adolescents and adults in a follow-up of
14 patients enrolled in two of the largest clinical trials of the drug in atopic dermatitis

15
16
17 *Ayen-Rodríguez A, Pereyra-Rodríguez JJ, Navarro-Triviño FJ, Alcantara-Luna
18 S, Domínguez-Cruz J, Galán-Gutiérrez M, et al. Long-Term Effectiveness and
19 Safety of Biologic and Small Molecule Drugs for Moderate to Severe Atopic
20 Dermatitis: A Systematic Review. *Life (Basel)*. 12 (8), 1159(2022)

21
22 Interesting systematic review on different molecules for the treatment of atopic
23 dermatitis, recommended reading.

24
25
26 *Drucker AM, Morra DE, Prieto-Merino D, Ellis AG, Yiu ZZN, Rochweg B, et
27 al. Systemic Immunomodulatory Treatments for Atopic Dermatitis: Update of a
28 Living Systematic Review and Network Meta-analysis. *JAMA Dermatol*. 158 (5),
29 523-532 (2022)

30
31 This systematic review and meta-analysis is one of the most important and
32 referenced in the literature, a must read.

33
34 *Pereyra-Rodríguez JJ, Herranz P, Figueras-Nart I, Perez B, Elosua M, Munera-

1 Campos M, et al. Treatment of severe atopic dermatitis with upadacitinib in real
2 clinical practice. Short-term efficacy and safety results. *J Investig Allergol Clin*
3 *Immunol.* 2022 Jun 2:0. doi: 10.18176/jiaci.0831. Epub ahead of print. PMID:
4 35671128.

5
6 One of the main articles published in RWE with upadacitinib in the Spanish
7 population, recommended reading.

8
9 *Chiricozzi A, Gori N, Narcisi A, Balato A, Gambardella A, Ortoncelli M,
10 Marzano AV, Balestri R, Palazzo G, Pellegrino M, Romanelli M, Tripepi G, Peris
11 K, Costanzo A; ACCURATE Group. Effectiveness and Safety of Upadacitinib in
12 the Treatment of Moderate-Severe Atopic Dermatitis: A Multicentric, Prospective,
13 Real-World, Cohort Study. *Drugs R D.* 22 (3), 245-252 (2022)

14
15 One of the main articles published in RWE with upadacitinib in the Italian
16 population, recommended reading.

17
18 *Feraru G, Nevet MJ, Samuelov L, Hodak E, Avitan-Hersh E, Ziv M, et al. Real-
19 life experience of upadacitinib for the treatment of adult patients with moderate-
20 to-severe atopic dermatitis - a case series. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol.* 36 (10),
21 e832-e833 (2022)

22
23 In the same year, new RWE data with upadacitinib is published, with relevant
24 reports for a better understanding of the drug.

25
26 *Kiefer S, König A, Gerger V, Rummenigge C, Müller AC, Jung T, et al. Efficacy
27 and Treatment Satisfaction of Different Systemic Therapies in Children and
28 Adolescents with Moderate-to-Severe Atopic Dermatitis: A Real-World Study. *J*
29 *Clin Med.* 12 (3), 1175 (2023)

30
31 First interesting article on RWE in paediatric and adolescent population with
32 upadacitinib, recommended reading.

Trial	Trial duration	Sample size	Comparator	Treatment arms	Primary endpoints	Results upadacitinib 15 mg	Results upadacitinib 30 mg
NCT03569293 Measure Up1 [12]	16 weeks	847	Placebo	Upadacitinib 15 mg QD Upadacitinib 30 mg QD Placebo QD	vIGA-AD 0/1 (% patients) EASI 75 (% patients)	% vIGA 0/1: 48% % EASI 75: 70% % EASI 90: 53% % EASI 100: 17% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 60%	% vIGA 0/1: 62% % EASI 75: 80% % EASI 90: 65.8% % EASI 100: 27% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 52%
NCT03607422 Measure Up2 [12]	16 weeks	836	Placebo	Upadacitinib 15 mg QD Upadacitinib 30 mg QD Placebo QD	vIGA-AD 0/1 (% patients) EASI 75 (% patients)	% vIGA 0/1: 39% % EASI 75: 60% % EASI 90: 42% % EASI 100: 14% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 60%	% vIGA 0/1: 52% % EASI 75: 73% % EASI 90: 59% % EASI 100: 19% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 42%
NCT03568318 AD Up [37]	16 weeks	901	Placebo + TCS	Upadacitinib 15 mg QD + TCS Upadacitinib 30 mg QD + TCS Placebo QD + TCS	vIGA-AD 0/1 (% patients) EASI 75 (% patients)	% vIGA 0/1: 40% % EASI 75: 65% % EASI 90: 43% % EASI 100: 12% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 51%	% vIGA 0/1: 59% % EASI 75: 77% % EASI 90: 63% % EASI 100: 23% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 64%
NCT03738397 (Phase 3b) Heads Up [13]	24 weeks	692	Dupilumab	Upadacitinib 30 mg QD Dupilumab 300 mg EOW	EASI 75 (% patients)	Not applicable	% vIGA 0/1: not applicable % EASI 75: 71% % EASI 90: 61% % EASI 100: 28% % pruritus NRS improvement \geq 4: 55%
NCT04195698* Heads Up (open label) (active, not recruiting)	52 weeks	692	Dupilumab	Upadacitinib 30 mg QD Dupilumab 300 mg EOW	EASI 75 (% patients)	Not applicable	Not applicable
NCT03661138** (Japan) Rising Up [38]	141 weeks	272	Placebo + TCS	Upadacitinib 15 mg QD + TCS Upadacitinib 30 mg QD + TCS Placebo QD + TCS	Number of participants experiencing adverse events [0n/PY (n/100 PY)]	Any AE 116/91.6 (126.6) Severe AE 16/274.8 (5.8) Serious AE 14/277.0 (5.1)	Any AE 117/66.6 (175.7) Severe AE 66/183.1 (36.0) Serious AE 8/276.8 (2.9)

1 Table 1. All clinical trials included patients with moderate severe atopic dermatitis in adults
2 (except AD Up, which also included adolescents aged 12 years and older), with vIGA (Investigator
3 Global Assessment) \geq 3, BSA (Body Surface Area) \geq 10%, EASI (Eczema Area and Severity Index)
4 \geq 16, and NRS (Numerical Rating Scale) pruritus scale \geq 4.

5

6 * Open-Label Extension Study of Upadacitinib in Adult Participants With Moderate to Severe
7 Atopic Dermatitis. <https://beta.clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT04195698>

8 **A Study to Evaluate Safety of Upadacitinib in Combination With Topical Corticosteroids in
9 Adolescent and Adult Participants With Moderate to Severe Atopic Dermatitis (Rising Up).
10 <https://beta.clinicaltrials.gov/study/NCT03661138>

11

12

1 Table 2. Research plan and ongoing studies of upadacitinib in atopic dermatitis.

ClinicalTrials.gov	Name	Phase	Sample size	Population	Treatment arms	Trial duration	Primary Outcome
NCT03646604	-	I	32	Pediatric [articipants (6–12 years) with severe AD	Upadacitinib	Not applicable	Cmax (Maximum Plasma Concentration) Tmax (Time to Maximum Observed Plasma Concentration) AUCtau (Area under the plasma concentrationtime curve within a dosing interval) Oral clearance Number of participants with treatment emergent adverse events
NCT03661138	Rising Up	III	272	Adolescents and adults (12–75 years) with moderate to severe atopic dermatitis	Upadacitinib + TCS or Placebo + TCS	141 weeks	Number of participants experiencing adverse events
NCT04195698	-	III	485	Adults (18–75 years) with moderate to severe AD, successfully completed treatment with either Dupilumab or Upadacitinib	Upadacitinib	52 weeks	Number of participants experiencing adverse events
NCT05507580	Flex-Up	IIIb/IV	600	Adults (18–64 years) with moderate to severe AD	Upadacitinib	12-24 weeks	% EASI 75 % EASI 90 % EASI 90 and WP-NRS of 0 or 1
NCT05394792	CAN UpTIMISE	Prospective Observational	100	Adults with moderate-to-severe AD, inadequate response or discontinuation of dupilumab	Upadacitinib	≥ 24 months	% vIGA 0/1
NCT05139836	Up-TAINED		772	Adults with AD (n = 772)	Upadacitinib	≥24 months	% participants achieving disease control Defined by ADCT total score
NCT05081557	AD-UISE		975	Adults and adolescents (≥12 Years Old) with AD	Upadacitinib	≥24 months	Upadacitinib utilization patterns vIGA-AD 0/1 vIGA-AD 0/1 among participants who achieved vIGA-AD 0/1 at Month 4

NCT05029895	-		170	Adolescents (≥12–18 Years) with AD	Upadacitinib	24 months	% participants with serious infection
NCT05451316	ADMIRE		200	Adolescents and adults (≥12) with moderate to severe prurigo-type AD	Upadacitinib	≥12 months	% achieving WP-NRS reduction ≥ 4

1